

STUDY ON THE THERMAL EXPANSION BEHAVIOR OF CARBON CARBON COMPOSITE DURING
CARBONIZATION PROCESS BY THERMAL MECHANICAL ANALYSIS TECHNIQUE

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ABSTRACT

Thermal expansion behavior, both unidirectionally reinforced pitch based carbon carbon composites heat treated up to 650°C and carbon fibers, was studied with high temperature thermal mechanical analyzer.

It was assumed that carbon carbon composite indicated an extreme anisotropic thermo-mechanical property not only as the graphitized composite but also as the composite on the way of fabrication during heat treatment procedure, and then one of the most important factors to produce high performance composites was the heating rate during heat treatment procedure which should be considered with the thermal expansion behavior of the materials.

Key words: Thermal expansion, carbon carbon composite and carbonization process.

1. INTRODUCTION

On the fabrication of carbon carbon composites, the selection of raw materials is the most important factor to achieve high performance, high strength and high modulus mechanical properties.

In spite of the proper selection for raw materials, the composite not always shows high performances on account of defects generated in the carbon matrix region or in the boundary between carbon fibers and carbon matrix, which is so-called cracks or delaminations.

These defects may correspond to the shrinkage-crack in the field of cokes and bulk graphite production. These defects might be generated by thermal stress during carbonization process(1) or on cooling from the heat treatment temperature(2).

For this stand point, it would be useful to investigate the thermal expansion behavior of carbon carbon composite precursor during heat treatment procedure.

The object of this study is to make sure of the thermal expansion behavior of carbon carbon composite on the way of fabrication during carbonization process.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

This study was performed with unidirectionally reinforced carbon carbon composite heat treated at 650°C.

2-1. MATERIALS

Petroleum pitch based carbon fiber (CARBONIC HM50 :PETOCA Ltd.) was used for reinforcement materials. And petroleum pitch (P-3 : PETOCA Ltd.) was used as carbon matrix precursor. The properties of these raw materials are listed in Table 1 and 2, respectively. The fabrication procedure of carbon carbon composites is shown in Figure 1.

The fiber was aligned unidirectionally on a mandrel using filament winding method. The mandrel was dipped into molten pitch at about 250°C and the pitch was impregnated under reduced pressure about 40 mmHg to make a carbon/pitch composite. The carbon/pitch composite cut into a proper size before the next treatment.

Carbonization was carried out in an autoclave at 650°C for 2 hours under 10 MPa nitrogen gas atmosphere. Samples carbonized in an autoclave were further once again impregnated by the molten pitch and carbonized in the same manner as mentioned above.

Apparent density of the sample was measured by Archimedes method. Bulk density was measured with the dimension and the weight. Open porosity was calculated from apparent and bulk density.

2-2. MEASUREMENT

The samples were machined into rectangular solid samples with the dimension of about 30 x 5 x 3 (mm). Measurement direction was corresponded to 30 mm length. The measurement directions of a parallel and of a vertical to fiber axes were denoted to " 0 " (zero) and " 90 " , respectively.

Thermal expansion behaviours of the composite in both parallel and vertical direction were measured from room temperature up to 2000°C (in situ) with heating rate 15°C/minute in Argon gas atmosphere.

SETARAM DHT 2400K Thermo Mechanical Analyzer System was used to perform this investigation. For the measurement of a carbon fiber, the fiber or film attachments made of graphite were applied.

Table 1. Properties of carbon fiber.
<CARBONIC HM50:PETOCA Ltd.>

Tensile strength	2,900 Mpa
Tensile modulus	500 GPa
Elongation	0.58 %
Density	2.15 g/cc
Number of filaments	2,000

Table 2. Properties of pitch.
<P-3:PETOCA Ltd .>

Softening point	151 °C
Fixed carbon	59 wt%
Toluene Insoluble	24 wt%
Quinoline Insoluble	0.05 wt%
Ash component	0.1 wt%

Figure 1. Fabrication procedure of carbon-carbon composite sample.

3. RESULTS

3-1. Thermal expansion behaviour of a carbon fiber.

Displacement curve and thermal expansion coefficient(TEC) curve are shown in Figure 2. Thermal shrinkage was observed from room temperature to about 350°C, and thermal expansion was observed from about 350°C to 2000°C. The average TEC of carbon fiber(HM50) from 500°C to 1600°C was calculated as $0.6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ 1/}^\circ\text{C}$. it was almost constant during this temperature range.

3-2. Thermal expansion behaviour of the composite precursor.

(1) 0° thermal expansion behaviour (In a parallel direction).

Displacement and TEC curves are shown in Figure 3. In the low temperature range under 800°C, the displacement curve showed almost the same pattern such as the curve of the carbon fiber HM50. But at 800°C, the slight shrinkage was detected. The shrinkage behavior was detected clearly from 650°C in the TEC curve. In the temperature range from 1200°C to about 1600°C, the TEC curve was observed stably constant. It was about $1.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ 1/}^\circ\text{C}$ at such a temperature range. This value was larger than that of carbon fiber ($0.6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ 1/}^\circ\text{C}$).

(2) 90° thermal expansion behaviour (In a vertical direction).

Displacement and TEC curves are shown in Figure 4. Thermal expansion was observed from room temperature to 800°C. In the temperature range higher than 800°C and lower than 1500°C, an extreme shrinkage was detected obviously. Such a tendency was shown clearly in the TEC curve. The TEC curve indicated that the shrinkage was occurring from nearly 650°C (original heat history of the composite), and this tendency of shrinkage continued up to 1500°C.

Figure 2. Thermal expansion behaviour of the carbon fiber HM50.
(DISPL: ———, TEC: - - - - -)

Figure 3. Thermal expansion behaviour of the carbon carbon composite heat treated at 650°C (in a parallel direction to fiber axis during carbonization up to 2000°C).
 (DISPL: ———, TEC: - - - - -)

Figure 4. Thermal expansion behaviour of the carbon carbon composite heat treated at 650°C (in a vertical direction to fiber axis during carbonization up to 2000°C).
 (DISPL: ———, TEC: - - - - -)

Figure 5. Thermal expansion behaviour of the carbon carbon composite heat treated at 2000°C (in a parallel direction to fiber axis during carbonization up to 2000°C).
 (DISPL: ———, TEC: - - - - -)

Figure 6. Thermal expansion behaviour of the carbon carbon composite heat treated at 2000°C during heat treatment up to 2000°C.

3-3. Thermal expansion behaviour of the carbonized composite.

Thermal expansion behaviours of the composite which were heat-treated at 2000°C were measured under the same manner.

In the parallel direction to fiber axis, the thermal expansion behaviour showed almost the same pattern as its reinforcement fiber without a significant shrinkage (Figure 5.). On the other hand, in the vertical direction to fiber axes a linear equational thermal expansion was indicated. Such an expansion is well known in the field of general molded graphite materials (Figure 6.). An average TEC of the composite (0°) was $0.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ 1/}^\circ\text{C}$ from 500°C to 1500°C. And that of the composite(90°) was $10.8 \times 10^{-6} \text{ 1/}^\circ\text{C}$ from room temperature to 2000°C. The TEC of the composite in a vertical direction to fiber axis was about 20 times larger than the coefficient in a parallel direction.

As a result, it was appreciated that carbon carbon composites indicated an extreme anisotropy at thermo-mechanical property not only as the graphitized composite but also as the composite on the way of fabrication during heat treatment.

4. DISCUSSION

The thermal expansion behaviour of an unidirectional reinforced carbon carbon composite in a parallel direction to fiber axis should be corresponded to its of the a-axis crystallite. And the expansion behaviour of a vertical direction to fiber axis should be corresponded to its of the c-axis crystallite.

R.J.Price and J.C.Bokros have investigated the relationship between the preferred orientation parameter and the TEC for various graphite (3).

The thermal expansion behaviour of the composite (0°) in a parallel direction to fiber axis would be reflected the behaviour of a carbon fiber expansion. This is the reason why the thermal expansion behaviour in a fiber axis direction shows a good similarity. But the TEC of the composite precursor heat treated at 650°C was larger than that of the reinforcement carbon fiber at the temperature range between 1200°C and 1600°C. The difference would depend on the characteristic of carbon matrix material which was on the way of heat treatment procedure. The orientation degree of the matrix must be lower than that of graphitized composite. On the other hand, the TEC of a graphitized composite showed a correspondence with the TEC of carbon fiber at the temperature range from 500°C to 1500°C. The TEC may be lower than that of a carbon fiber. It is surmised that the stress, caused by thermal shrinkage observed in a vertical direction, effects the orientation of crystallite in carbon matrices or carbon fibers (4).

In the parallel direction to fiber axis, the composite precursor heat treated at 650°C showed 0.164 % displacement expansion on heating process up to 2000°C (in situ). And 0.124 % displacement shrinkage, which correspond to the thermal expansion behaviour of the composite heat treated at 2000°C, may be observed on cooling process to room temperature. Therefore, the slight residual stress might be induced on account of the difference for displacement ($0.04 \% = 0.164 - 0.124$).

In the vertical direction to fiber axis, the composite showed an extreme thermal shrinkage (about 3.03 %) during heat treatment up to 2000°C (in situ). On the way of cooling to room temperature the shrunk composite would indicate a thermal shrinkage (2.22 %) corresponded to the expansion behaviour of the composite heat treated at 2000°C. Consequently, for the composite precursor heat treated at 650°C, the thermal shrinkage (5.25 %) may be observed after heat treatment at 2000°C.

As the residual displacement in the parallel direction, it was a negligibly small and the residual permanent displacement in the vertical direction was 5.25 %, the volume shrinkage should be estimated easily about 10.23 %.

These thermal expansion behaviour must influence on the fundamental physical

properties which are compiled in Table 3. The weight loss of the composite precursor heat treated at 650°C was about 4.5 % after heat treatment up to 2000°C. The change of the bulk density, which is 1.720 g/cc to 1.842 g/cc with 4.5 % weight loss after heat treatment at 2000°C is explained by the volume shrinkage of the composite (9.95 %). This calculated shrinkage shows a good agreement with the examined result. And then, in the case of the apparent density change, the calculated volume shrinkage must be about 13.8 %. There is a difference by 3.6 % between the calculated (13.8 %) and the result (10.2 %). This difference may be contributed to generation of some defects such as evaluated open porosity. The open porosity increased from 7.1 % to 11.1 % after heat treatment at 2000 °C . The increased 4.0 % open porosity should be corresponded to the 3.6 % gaps of a volume shrinkage between the calculated and the result.

Therefore, it was assumed that the apparent volume shrinkage would be reduced by the generation of defects recognized such as open pores. In anyway, some kinds of defects which mean crack, delamination, residual stress etc. occur during carbonization process.

Since the apparent extreme volume shrinkage of the composite depends mainly on the shrinkage in a vertical direction to fiber axis, it is suggested that the most considerable treatment for carbonization must be carried out from 650°C to 1500°C, especially at 800-900 °C.

Table 3. Fundamental physical properties of the composites before and after heat treatment at 2000°C.

Sample	Vf (%)	Bulk density (g/cc)	Apparent density (g/cc)	Open porosity (%)
Before	48	1.72 ₀	1.85 ₂	7.1
After	57	1.82 ₄	2.05 ₁	11.1

CONCLUSION

Thermal expansion behaviour of unidirectional carbon carbon composite heat treated at 650°C was investigated in both a parallel and a vertical direction to fiber axis during carbonization process up to 2000°C. The composite indicates an extreme anisotropic thermal expansion behaviour. In a parallel direction, a negligibly small thermal expansion was observed. But in a vertical direction, an extreme shrinkage was observed.

Since the shrinkage should be relate to the generation of defects, it is suggested that the heat treatment procedure should be considered with the thermal expansion behaviour of the materials.

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